

THE ROLE OF NANOTECHNOLOGY IN MODERN PHYSICS.

Bobokulova Muxtaram Khamroyevna

Asian International University

Assistant of the "General Technical Sciences" department

Dear Mr. Bobokulova607@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10570465>

ANNOTATION.

Nanotechnology consists of techniques and technologies based on the production and control of nano-sized data in an embedded area of materials, devices and measurements. Nano data is used in the form of particles (nanoparticles) consisting of atoms and molecules. It is widely used to create more efficient techniques in technology, energy efficiency, scientific research, medicine and other fields. "Nanotechnology" and "physics" are both sciences of great importance in the scientific, technological and practical spheres of mankind. However, in the process of developing nanotechnologies and their implementation, its environmental and safety issues are also important. Nanoparticles have their own characteristics. due to their presence, their impact on life and environment should be evaluated frequently.

Keywords : nano-materials, nano-chip, electronics, satellites.

Enter

Currently, many areas and fields related to nanotechnology and physics are undergoing further development and creation. These two disciplines play a major role in creating new, effective techniques by providing complementary information and methods to each other. Nanotechnology is a scientific field and practice involving technologies related to the development and manipulation of materials and devices at very small dimensions, and is of great importance. This includes the development, control and use of technology, nanomaterials and nanodata. Nanotechnology is widely used in various fields, and its importance is as follows: Nanotechnology is developing in the creation of nanomaterials composed of atoms and molecules. They are used in many areas such as increasing energy consumption, reducing volume, extending the shelf life of food products, and so on, as they offer great performance in a small size.

Importance in the field of medicine: Nanotechnology is widely used in the field of medicine. Nano-materials are used to make medical devices smaller, more efficient and more flexible. Nanochips, nanosensors and other nanodevices are important for the diagnosis, treatment and improvement of medical processes.

Development in the field of energy: Nanotechnology, increasing energy consumption, improving batteries and accumulators, creating self-charging

devices, plays an important role in the development of energy consumption technologies. This helps to reduce the wastage of energy sources and to learn about the variability of the light set.

Food industry and water conservation: Nanotechnology is used in the food industry and plays an important role in water conservation. Nanomaterials include light packaging and safety in food storage and transportation.

Making small tools and devices: Nanotechnology is also important in making small tools and devices used in electronics and other industries. They help to create fast and efficient tools.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

For all these reasons, nanotechnologies have great potential to provide effective and innovative solutions that are widely used in all areas of our lives and serve to bring about great changes in our daily lives. Nanotechnologies are also widely used in the field of radio engineering and provide additional advantages to other technologies in this field. The indications from these important experimental areas show that nanotechnology will be of great importance in bringing about the development of transformative solutions and innovative applications in the field of radio engineering.

In cosmonautics, nanotechnology is widely used in foreign tourists, orbiters and other space devices. These technologies are used in the creation of new solutions and tools in the field of aerospace, in the development of effective solutions and materials in space, moderate light and heat reviews, in solving technological problems in many conditions, and in the performance of space devices and probes. The following important points show the use of nanotechnology in aerospace: Nano-materials are used in the development of small and efficient antennas. Antennas made of nano-materials are widely used for wearable electronics, sensors and communication devices. Their effective properties are important for the operational support and characteristics of radio equipment. Nano-chips are effective devices for microchips used in radio equipment and other integrated devices that also use nano-materials produced in them. This ensures that the device is smaller, faster, energy-efficient and safer than other devices. Nanotubes and nanocomposites are especially used in the field of radio engineering. They can be configured for consumers, antennas, cables and other means. These materials are used to reduce light and to overcome the influence of external factors. Nano-sensors offer great opportunities for radio engineering devices. They play an important role in detecting the surrounding variables, controlling the state of the device, and

gathering the necessary information for communication tools. Nano-devices are used in the development of radio systems in radio engineering. They play an important role in the creation of innovative solutions in the field of fast signal transmission, signal analysis and radio engineering. The results from these important experimental areas are of great importance in bringing about the development of revolutionary solutions and innovative applications of nanotechnology in the field of radio engineering. indicates that it will have Nanotechnology is also widely used in the field of radio engineering and adds additional advantages to other technologies in this field. Nanotechnology is used in radio engineering at the following important points: Nano-materials are used in the development of small-sized and efficient antennas. Antennas made of nano-materials are widely used for wearable electronics, sensors and communication devices. Their effective properties are important for the performance and performance of radio engineering devices. Nano-chips are effective devices for microchips and other integrated devices used in radio engineering devices, which also use nano-materials. . This ensures that the device is smaller, faster, more energy efficient and safer than other devices. Nanotubes and nanocomposites are specially used in the field of radio engineering. They can be configured for consumers, antennas, cables and other means. These materials are used to reduce light and to overcome the influence of external factors.

Nano-sensors offer great opportunities for radio engineering devices. They play an important role in determining the variables around them, controlling the state of the device, and gathering the necessary information for the means of communication . Nano-materials are used to create new solutions for solar modules and batteries. They play an important role in the rapid acquisition of light, the development of energy-efficient technologies and the provision of energy for spacecraft.

Nano-materials and nano-devices play an important role in light storage and heat control in space vehicles. They are also important in developing comfortable, efficient and lightweight materials for astronauts. Satellites (cars, airplanes, and other vehicles) are an area with great potential for the use of nanotechnology. Nano-materials and nano-technologies help provide vehicles with better visibility, light reduction, speed and performance. The following highlights the application of nanotechnology in satellites: Nano-materials are mutually important in reducing the weight of satellites and increasing their brightness. Satellites using efficient nano-materials reduce energy consumption

and increase brightness. Nano-technologies are used to improve the heating and cooling control systems, insulation and internal temperature control of satellites. This is important to reduce energy consumption. Nano-devices are used to make energy efficient satellites' batteries and collect light. They have the properties to change the conditions of the electrical level and help to ensure the long-term operation of the batteries of the cars. Nano-materials are used to improve the visibility and other elements of satellites. This is important for the size, shape and design of cars. Nano-technologies are used to improve the safety systems of satellites. Nanomaterials are used to reduce weight and create materials that can be dark, fire, time very fast. indicates that 'rin takes over. These technologies are of great importance in the creation of new solutions and tools in the field of transportation, and may indicate an innovative development between cars, airplanes and other vehicles in the future.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Nanotechnology has great potential to advance several areas that play an important role in television applications. In these areas, nanotechnology is used to improve lighting, signal transmission, screen quality, and other features. The following important points show the application of nanotechnology in television: Nano- materials are used to create screens used in television. A number of nano-materials show their potential in the development of OLED (organic LED) screens. It has screens, recolors, getting light in a short time, reducing energy consumption and other important features. Nano-devices are used to make signal transmission systems used in television more efficient. They help in providing fast, strong and good signal. This will improve the quality of the signal and enable the latest technological developments in television. Nano-devices are also used to make the batteries used in television more efficient. This is important in providing increased power consumption and increased speed. Nano-solutions for batteries can help maintain long-lasting performance and light. Nano-sensors are used in the creation of convenience and automation tools used in television. They can help you automate your TV practice, provide advice and other opportunities. Nano-technologies are used to control light and heat in devices used in television. This can help reduce energy consumption, provide light and efficient features in the heating and cooling management of devices. Nano-materials are also used in the plastic part of devices used in television. They are used to create effective and light materials for the size and structure of plastic sleeves. Nanotechnology plays an important role in providing effective and innovative solutions, well reviewed on television. These technologies are

used to improve the quality of televisions and other devices, provide them better and create new opportunities.

Nanotechnologies have great potential in creating effective solutions and applications in the field of medicine and are used in various areas of medicine. Nano-materials, nano-chips, nano-sensors and other nano-devices play an important role in the creation of new solutions and tools in the treatment, diagnostics, practices and other fields of medicine.

The following important points indicate the application of nanotechnology in the field of medicine:

Nano-materials and nano-chips are used to create effective techniques in the treatment of diseases and other medical processes. Nano-materials contain sources of medicine (butts, ointments, gels and other means) and fix them at a certain point. Nano-chips are used in applications to improve scientific research and treatment. Nano-sensors are used to improve disease diagnosis and treatment processes. They help to increase the time required for laboratory tests with ease and speed. Nano-sensors are placed on medical devices and used to collect other data. Nano-materials are used in the development of medical materials. They are used to quickly and efficiently heal wound tissues, create implants, and improve medical devices. Nano-materials are important in creating medical materials that are resistant to biodegradation and other harmful effects. It is also used to create effective solutions in the field of nanotechnologies, DNA and genomic technologies. They are used for elucidation, analysis and genetic therapy of genetic structures. Nano-materials and nano-devices are used in the prevention and treatment of diseases. Their small size plays an important role in creating effective solutions for food structure. Nanotechnologies are of great importance in technological developments in the field of medicine, in the creation of new solutions and tools in the field of treatment, diagnosis and detection of diseases. plays an important role. Nanotechnology and radiobiology, sciences that work together in the treatment of diseases and solving problems related to radiation. Radiobiology is the study of the substances and systems of life based on radiation, while nanotechnology refers to technologies related to the creation of materials and devices using nano-diodes, nano-chips and other nano-devices. The important points shared by both these fields can be shown as follows. Radiotherapy is a technique that involves the use of radiation to treat disease. Nanotechnology improves the devices used in radiotherapy to target only the diseased substance at the target diseased site. Nano-materials and nano-chips are used to ensure effective and

well-controlled radiotherapy. Nano-materials are used to create nanoparticles that are used for radiation control. These nanoparticles are used to control the level, types and properties of radiation, as well as to reduce the radiation dose of diseased food products or other substances used in medicine. used in learning. It helps to understand how radiation can change life, explain the dangers of radiation, and control radiation based on diseased foods. Nano-materials are used in the structure of radioactive substances and their closer control from food products. This provides effective solutions for reducing radiation dose, creating techniques that can only be used in the field of radiation, in the treatment of disease or radiation. Nanotechnology is used in radiological imaging and diagnostics. Nano-materials are used to improve the process of radiological imaging, to develop new technologies for radiological culture media and diagnostic equipment. They are used in the creation of innovative solutions for the treatment of radiation-related problems and diseases, in the diagnosis of disease and in radiation-based research.

Summary

Nanotechnology and engineering are complementary and interconnected fields of technology. Nanotechnology, nanomaterials, nanodevices, nanosensors, and other nano-scales are engineering solutions that include the creation of materials and devices, diagnostics, treatment, and many other areas of innovation. The following key points outline the connections between nanotechnology and engineering. Nanotechnology helps in the use of nano-materials in the creation of technical tools. These materials make technical tools efficient, lightweight, energy efficient and have other supporting features. Nano-devices are used to make technical tools efficient and create new technical innovations. They play an important role in improving the performance of cars, computers, smart devices and other technical equipment.

These connections between nanotechnology and technology play a major role in creating new solutions and innovations. They help each other in the field of better review, production and use of technical tools through new materials, devices and technological solutions.

Nanotechnology and information technology are interrelated and interrelated fields of technology. It emphasizes the interdependence of these two fields in developing new solutions, materials and technological innovations, making them more efficient, stronger and more informative. These connections between nanotechnology and the development of society mutually support the

production of new solutions and techniques, the innovative and economic development of society.

Used literature:

1. Quvvatov, B. (2024). SQL DATABASES AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS: NAVIGATING THE DATA MANAGEMENT LANDSCAPE. В DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 117–124).
2. Quvvatov, B. (2024). CONSTRUCTION OF SPECIAL MODELS THROUGH DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS. В SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 108–115).
3. Quvvatov, B. (2024). FINDING SOLUTIONS OF SPECIAL MODELS BY INTEGRATING INTEGRAL EQUATIONS AND MODELS. В CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 122–130).
4. Quvvatov, B. (2024). GLOBAL IN VIRTUAL LEARNING MOBILE APP CREATION INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES. В SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 95–104).
5. Quvvatov, B. (2024). WEB FRONT-END AND BACK-END TECHNOLOGIES IN PROGRAMMING. В THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 208–215).
6. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. li.(2023). Mobil ilovalar yaratish va ularni bajarish jarayoni. International journal of scientific researchers, 2(2).
7. Behruz Ulug'bek o'g, Q. (2023). USE OF ARTIFICIAL NERVOUS SYSTEMS IN MODELING. Multidisciplinary Journal of Science and Technology, 3(5), 269-273.
8. Karimov, F. (2022). ANIQ INTEGRALNI TAQRIBIY HISOBLASH. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz), 14(14).
9. Quvvatov, B. (2024). GLOBAL IN VIRTUAL LEARNING MOBILE APP CREATION INFORMATION SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES. Science and innovation in the education system, 3(1), 95-104.
10. Quvvatov, B. (2024). SQL DATABASES AND BIG DATA ANALYTICS: NAVIGATING THE DATA MANAGEMENT LANDSCAPE. Development of pedagogical technologies in modern sciences, 3(1), 117-124.
11. Quvvatov, B. (2024). CONSTRUCTION OF SPECIAL MODELS THROUGH DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS AND PRACTICAL SOLUTIONS. Solution of social problems in management and economy, 3(1), 108-115.
12. Quvvatov, B. (2024). FINDING SOLUTIONS OF SPECIAL MODELS BY INTEGRATING INTEGRAL EQUATIONS AND MODELS. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 3(1), 122-130.

13. Quvvatov, B. (2024). WEB FRONT-END AND BACK-END TECHNOLOGIES IN PROGRAMMING. Theoretical aspects in the formation of pedagogical sciences, 3(1), 208-215.
14. Behruz Ulugbek og, Q. (2023). TECHNOLOGY AND MEDICINE: A DYNAMIC PARTNERSHIP. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11).
15. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED SYSTEM FOR CONTROLLING TEMPERATURE AND HUMIDITY IN PRODUCTION ROOMS. В DEVELOPMENT AND INNOVATIONS IN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
16. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. В ACADEMIC RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 2, сс. 16–27).
17. Muradov, O. (2024). BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS. В MODELS AND METHODS IN MODERN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 84–93).
18. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLIED TO THE CURRENT TRAINING PROCESS REQUIREMENTS. В INNOVATIVE RESEARCH IN SCIENCE (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 54–63).
19. Muradov, O. (2024). APPLICATION OF BASIC PRINCIPLES AND RULES OF INNOVATIVE PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES TO EDUCATIONAL PROCESSES. В МЕЖДУРОДНАЯ КОНФЕРЕНЦИЯ АКАДЕМИЧЕСКИХ НАУК (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 46–55).
20. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). DATA BY COMBINING MAIL THROUGH TO SEND METHODS. В THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 198–207).
21. Akhmedova, Z., & Rahmatova, N. (2024). LMS (LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM) LEARNING MANAGEMENT SYSTEM FEATURES. В SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE EDUCATION SYSTEM (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 85–94).
22. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). IPHONE OPERATIONAL IN THE SYSTEM MOBILE APPLICATIONS TO CREATE INTENDED PROGRAMMING ENVIRONMENTS. В CURRENT APPROACHES AND NEW RESEARCH IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 111–121).
23. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). STRUCTURES OF SMALL DATABASE MANAGEMENT SYSTEMS. В SOLUTION OF SOCIAL PROBLEMS IN MANAGEMENT AND ECONOMY (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 97–107).

24. Akhmedova, Z. (2024). CREATION OF A DATABASE FOR THE SYSTEM PLATFORM OF NON-GOVERNMENT EDUCATIONAL CENTERS. В DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN MODERN SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 1, сс. 106–116).
25. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). SQL SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA ANALYSIS. Science and innovation in the education system, 2(13), 113-120.
26. Akhmedova, Z. (2023). DISADVANTAGES OF ELECTRONIC LEARNING. Current approaches and new research in modern sciences, 2(12), 99-109.
27. Murodov, O. (2024). DEVELOPMENT OF AN AUTOMATED PARAMETER CONTROL SYSTEM ROOMS AND WORKSHOPS BASED ON CLOUD TECHNOLOGIES. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(2), 16-27.
28. INNOVATIVE INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES AND NEW METHODS AND TOOLS FOR THEIR APPLICATION IN TODAY'S EDUCATION
29. OT MURODOV - International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & ..., 2023
30. Jurakulov, S. (2023). PHYSICAL-MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF NA-KMS AND CARBAPOLL BASED GELS. Development and innovations in science, 2(12), 65-70.
31. Jurakulov, S. (2023, December). RESEARCH THEORIES OF PHYSICS COURSES IN JAPAN. In Международная конференция академических наук (Vol. 2, No. 12, pp. 43-48).16:08